

Problems and Profile of Women Entrepreneurs in Ramanathapuram District

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Abstract

There is no welfare of the nation unless the condition of women is improved.

- Swami Vivekananda

The entrepreneurs play an important role in the economic and social development of the nation. Entrepreneurship refers to the act of setting up a new business so as to take advantages from new opportunities. The dependency on service sector has created many entrepreneurial opportunities for women that they can utilize to enhance their social standing and reputation. Women entrepreneurs are also giving a partial role in this field. Nowadays, society gives a better socio economic status to women. In this paper, an attempt has been made to study the problems related have entrepreneurship that the woman of our country faces at present.

Keywords: Women, Entrepreneur, Entrepreneurship and Problems

Introduction

In the developing economies, the need for entrepreneurship has been familiar as the key factor of growth of an economy. Women are generally perceived as home makers with little to do with economy or commerce. But this picture is changing nowadays. In Modern India, more and more women are taking up entrepreneurial activity especially in medium and small scale enterprises. Women have been successful in breaking their confinement within the limits of their homes by entering into varied kinds of professionals and services. Women entrepreneurs have proved to be on par with their men counterparts in business acumen and are emerging as smart and dynamic entrepreneurs. Besides this, today, a network of institutions exists in the country to promote women entrepreneurship. The commercial banks and the financial institution are an integral part of this network. Many organizations / institutions and association promote and develop women entrepreneurship by providing financial assistance at concessional rates of interest and also organize industrial fairs and exhibitions. Entrepreneurship Development Programme for women creates entrepreneurial awareness among them.

The Objectives of the Study

The present study has been carried out with the following objectives

1. To study the socio-economic background of the women entrepreneurs in Ramanathapuram district.
2. To analyze the major problems of women entrepreneurs which affect the women entrepreneurship
3. To offer findings and suggestions to improve the satisfaction of women entrepreneurs and to framework for the promotion of women entrepreneurship of selected district in TamilNadu.

Research Methodology

Sample Size: The sample size was fixed to 90 women entrepreneurs in Ramanathapuram District.

Sampling Method: ‘Convenient’ sampling method is used for this study

Source of Data: For this study both primary and secondary data are used. Primary data are collected directly from 90 women entrepreneurs in Ramanathapuram District. Secondary data are collected from journals and publications, books, relevant website etc.

Area of the Study: Ramanathapuram district in southern Tamil Nadu has been selected for the study as it is considered as the backward district in the economic condition.

Tools for Data Collection: Primary data were collected through direct discussion, and interview. The collection of information from women entrepreneurs, questionnaire and interview schedule were used.

Tools for Analysis: Simple percentage Analysis and Weighted average score are the statistical tools applied in the study.

Table 1 Personal Profile of the Respondents / Socio-Economic Characteristics

1. Table one that 35.56% of the respondents are belong to 30 - 40 years age group of the entrepreneurs. 28.89% of the respondents are between the age group of 40 - 50 year. The 22.22% of the respondents are below the 30 years age group and rest of the respondents is above the 50 years. 69% of the respondents are married and rests of the respondents belong to unmarried category. Therefore, marital status is important factor to determine the women entrepreneurs. 46.67% of the respondents are belonging to higher secondary level of the entrepreneurs. 20% of the respondents are graduates and 17.78% of the respondents are secondary level of education. The 10% of the respondents are primary level, and rests of the respondent are illiterates. 35.56% of the respondents are belonging to 10,000 to 20,000 incomes of families. 23.33% of the respondents are Rs. 20,000 to 30,000 income group and only 8% of the respondents are their family income of above 40,000.

Factors	Category	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Age 90	Below 30	20	22.22
	30-40	32	35.56
	40-50	26	28.89
	Above 50	12	13.33
Marital Status	Unmarried	21	21
	Married	69	69

Factors	Category	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Educational Qualification	Illiterate	5	5.56
	Primary	9	10
	Secondary	16	17.78
	Higher Secondary	42	46.67
	Graduate and above	18	20
Monthly Income	Below 10,000	15	16.67
	10,000 – 20,000	32	35.56
	20,000 – 30,000	21	23.33
	30,000 – 40,000	14	15.56
	40,000 and above	8	8.89

Table 2 Sources of Funds for Investment in the business

S.No.	Sources of Fund	No. of respondents	Percentage
1	Personal Savings	27	30
2	Spouse Income	32	35
3	Bank loan	23	25.56
4	Others	8	8

Table 2 that 35% of the finance sources from spouse income, 30% of the respondents financed from personnel savings, and 25.56% are loan from banks as well as 8% respondent’s financial sources are other sources.

Table 3 Type of Business Activity undertaken by the Respondents

S.No.	Type of Business activity	No. of respondents	Percentage
1	Manufacturing	38	42.22
2	Trading	23	25.56
3	Service	20	22.22
4	Combined	9	10.00
		90	100

Table-3 that 42.22% of the respondents are deals with manufacturing types of business. 25.56% of the respondents who was engaged in trading type of business. Only 22.22% of the respondents are doing our business for service sectors, and 10% of the respondents are combined all type of business.

Table 4 Problems of Women Entrepreneurs

S.No.	Problems	SA	A	M	DA	SDA	Total	AVG Score	Rank
1	Financial Constraints	31	41	12	4	2	365	4.05	III
2	Lack of leadership	25	38	17	6	4	344	3.82	VI
3	Lack of family support	33	31	15	7	4	352	3.91	IV
4	Health problem	27	39	11	8	5	345	3.83	V
5	Non-awareness of Govt Scheme	21	23	22	13	11	300	3.33	IX
6	Lack of education	38	33	11	5	3	368	4.08	II

7	Lack of knowledge on latest technology	44	28	9	5	4	373	4.14	I
8	Lack of marketing skills	28	32	14	9	7	327	3.63	VIII
9	Low ability to bear risk	21	41	13	8	7	331	3.68	VII

Source: Primary Data

SA – Strongly Agree, A - Agree, M – Moderately Agree, DA - Disagree, SDA – Strongly Disagree

Table 4 that Problems faced by women entrepreneurs, the weighted ranking method applied. It inferred that the most number of the respondents had given the first ranked for Lack of knowledge on latest technology; the respondents had given the Second rank for Lack of education. The third rank was Financial Constraints, and followed by Lack of family support, Health problem, Lack of leadership, Low ability to bear risk, Lack of marketing skills, Non-awareness of Govt Scheme.

Suggestions

1. Most of the women entrepreneurs are of the opinion that because of lack of training, they are not able to survive in the market. Hence, the government should conduct frequent training programmes with regard to new production techniques, sales techniques, etc; this training should be made compulsory for women entrepreneurs.
2. Finance is the first major problem for women entrepreneurs. Hence, the government has to provide interest free loans to encourage women entrepreneurs. To attract more women entrepreneurs, subsidy for loans should be increased..
3. Separate seminar or conference may be organized to make the women to know the various beneficial schemes and support of the Govt to promote women entrepreneurs
4. A separate awareness program can be arranged to make the husband and parents to be aware and helpful to the women entrepreneurs.
5. Marketing the product is one of the main problems for women entrepreneurs. Here, women co-operative societies can be started to procure the products from women entrepreneurs. They will help them in selling their products at a reasonable price.

Conclusion

Women entrepreneurship is a recent phenomenon. But to be a successful entrepreneur, Women have to face various problems. It is evident from the study that women are ready to face the challenges associated with setting up of business. Though there are many challenges to be faced by the women in the business sector, they do not give up their initiatives taken to succeed in the field. Society is very much receptive to the concept of women entrepreneur. Women are not into the business for survival but to satisfy their inner urge of creativity and to prove their capabilities. Women education is contributing to a great extent to the social transformation. The society in future will meet more women venturing into the areas traditionally dominated by men.

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